

2016
SUSTAINABILITY
REPORT

ELLOS GROUP

ellos Jotex STAYHARD

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INTERVIEW WITH THE PRESIDENT AND CEO

What are the driving forces behind your sustainability efforts?

- We want to build a business that can be part of the solution, and see sustainability as a key to stay competitive in future.

Four areas that receive extra attention in our work are; sustainable materials, fair working conditions and human rights and anti-corruption.

What are the trends prevailing in society that inspire your work?

- I can see three main trends; digitalization and connected society, climate change and scarce resources and finally globalization. To be successful today you need to be proactive and agile to adapt to these trends, mitigate risks and seize opportunities.

What are your most important environmental challenges?

- The textiles and apparel sector is a large user of natural resources, including water and petroleum. Other environmental topics in the fashion industry include the heavy use of chemicals in the supply chain, and the industry's contribution to a "wear and tear" consumption pattern. We can only become successful by addressing these issues. One thing we focus on is to make better choices of the materials we use. We are for example part

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To be successful today you need to be proactive and agile to adapt to these trends, mitigate risks and seize opportunities.

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of Better Cotton Initiative, BCI, which has the mission to make global cotton production better for the environment it grows in, for the people who produce it and for the sector's future. I am proud to say that sustainable cotton today represents 46 percent of our cotton range, an increase of 36 percentage points in 2016. We are

also part of Sweden Textile Water Initiative, STWI, with the mission to gain a better understanding of the water challenges faced by the industry and finding the right mechanisms to address them. These are two examples and there are many more as you will read in this

report. We work continually to improve efficiency by utilizing existing resources in a better way, and we build cooperation and partnerships with companies and with society, which gives us a better chance of influencing things.

You are sourcing products from developing countries, which may be a challenge regarding working conditions and other social issues. How do you address this?

- As a responsible company in this sector we see many opportunities for contributing to better working conditions in developing countries. We work closely with our suppliers for fair working conditions in our supply chain. We have a Suppliers Code of Conduct and a detailed Supplier's guide, which are both compulsory. During 2017, we will seek to have an assessment report from most of our suppliers' factories. An example of how we take responsibility for working conditions is that in 2016 we joined the Accord in Bangladesh, an independent, legally-binding agreement between companies and unions, to secure safe and healthy working employment in this important emerging market.

In what way do you contribute to a more sustainable consumption when it comes to the use of fashion?

- We strive for a timeless and high quality range that our customers can keep using for a longer period of time, and we encourage our customers to recycle their used clothes and textiles.

When you look back at 2016, what were your most important achievements for ensuring that your sustainability remains good?

- I was particularly happy about establishing our new Code of Ethics and the rollout of our Code of Conduct throughout the entire organization. In addition to this we also added an external whistleblowing system and published our first Sustainability report.

For the Ellos Group it is important to address societal challenges with innovative solutions based on profitable business practices. We want, for example, to do what we can to contribute to a greater diversity, both in society and at our company. The "Mitt Liv" partner program is an excellent tool for better capitalizing on the expertise that exists in our country in the form of people who have recently arrived. In 2016 we established cooperation with "Mitt Liv" with the aim of increasing diversity at our company, while at the same time contributing to integrate people with a foreign background in the Swedish workforce.

I am happy to see how the awareness about sustainability issues today is influencing the whole organization and how it has become a natural and value-creating part of the daily business.

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read 'Hans Ohlsson'.

Hans Ohlsson, CEO

The Ellos Group is a leading Nordic e-commerce platform in fashion and home furnishings. The portfolio of online stores consists of Ellos, Stayhard and Jotex, each a market leader in their market segments. Ellos is the online department store for women (fashion, home and beauty), Jotex is the online home interior expert, and Stayhard is the leading fashion destination for men. We continually strive to develop market-leading consumer brands and to build close relationships with our customers. Our own brands are the foundation, supplemented in our range by selected external brands.

We are proud of the heritage of the Ellos Group, which goes back to 1947 when Olle Blomqvist started Ellos. The cornerstone has been a strong entrepreneurial and merchant culture that is still an important part of who we are. Over the years, success has been built on a close relationship with the customer, a passion to deliver value and develop products and services. Over the past three years, the Ellos Group has undertaken a major transformation to become a modern e-commerce player. We believe that the strong platform we have built, as well as the ability to transform, will enable us to generate continued profitable and sustainable growth.

Governance Structure

The Board of Directors is the highest governance body of the Ellos Group. The Board consists of the chairman of the Board and six Board members. In addition, four employee representatives are part of the Board of Directors. For the purpose of handling specific matters, the Board has established the following committees: Audit Committee and Remuneration Committee. The Board of Directors is responsible for establishing business objectives and strategy, ensuring that there is satisfactory control of the Group's compliance with laws and regulations, and ensuring that key policies are adopted for the Group.

The progress of the sustainability work of the Group is followed-up bi-annually in the board and monthly in the management team. The center of expertise, strategic and tactical work is secured by the Sustainability Director, who is part of the management team. The implementation and follow-up of the sustainability actions are driven by the head of each function.

THREE ONLINE STORES:

ellos Jotex
STAYHARD

SALES & OPERATIONS IN

- Founded 1947 in Borås, Sweden
- Head Office and logistic hub located in Borås
- Design and production of own brands and over 500 external brands in the portfolio
- Turnover 2016: SEK 2.1 billion
- Employees: around 700
- Active customers: around 1.6 million (customers placing an order within the last 12 months)
- Ownership: majority-owned by Nordic Capital since 2013

OUR CORPORATE CULTURE

We are proud of who we are at the Ellos Group, what we stand for and where we are heading. Since 1947, our success has been driven by innovation and creativity. We care for and nurture our identity, our heritage and our expertise.

OUR VISION

To be the leading e-commerce platform in the Nordic region in fashion and home furnishings.

OUR VALUES

- We are proud and passionate
- We are strong together
- We believe in a frank dialogue - and the freedom to speak out
- We are brave and take responsibility
- We deliver "High Touch - Low Cost"

WE ARE ON AN EXCITING JOURNEY

”

2016 was a very positive year for the Ellos Group from a sustainability perspective. This was the first year of executing our new sustainability strategy, and we have taken major steps in several of our most important areas from a materiality perspective. To highlight a few of the achievements, we have significantly increased the share of sustainable cotton products, reaching 46% in 2016. We have also increased the audit and inspection coverage of all our suppliers from 27% in 2015 to 77% in 2016. We have only started the journey towards becoming a sustainable company.

We will continue to work towards our goals for 2020, which will require effort from us and from our partners and suppliers. This will be an exciting journey for the Group.

During 2016, we also defined how our actions and projects are contributing to the Sustainable Development Goals. Our work over the year has directly supported eight of the goals. We believe that as a business we have an important role to play to achieve sustainable change, together with our stakeholders, and we will continue to work on how we can support even more of the Sustainable Development Goals going forward.

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*Annika Mårtensson
Business Development and
Sustainability Director,
Ellos Group*

46%

sustainable cotton in our assortment 2016.

Top 100 employer of the year 2016!

In 2016, Ellos Group reached **77%** coverage of all suppliers with valid audits or inspections, up from 27% in 2015.

New plastic bags in **renewable plastics**, resulting in 60% lower CO₂ emissions per bag.

70%

From 2013 to 2016 we **reduced our customer mailings by 70%**, which equals 8500 tonnes of paper.

In June 2016 Ellos Group signed the **Accord on Fire and Building Safety in Bangladesh**.

SUSTAINABILITY

AT THE ELLOS GROUP

Sustainability is a natural and value-creating part of the daily business at the Ellos Group. A sustainable business approach with a long-term perspective challenges us to be innovative, curious and transparent, and creates value for our customers, employees, business partners, and owners, as well as for the communities in which we operate. We want to contribute to a better world for future generations and aspire to building a business that can be part of the solution.

Customers

We believe in transparency and a friendly, respectful and supportive communication. Our customers can always trust our generous advice, and our products to be safe and responsibly produced.

The Team

We treat each other with mutual respect and provide equal opportunities in a healthy, safe and creative working environment. The competence, loyalty and entrepreneurial drive of our team enable us to reach our goals. Our key to success is constant progress.

Suppliers

We expect our suppliers and business partners to share our views about business ethics, human rights, fair working conditions and the environment. We believe in co-operation and work with our suppliers to continually improve the sustainability of our value chain.

Environment

We strive to contribute to a sustainable future by using natural resources more efficiently and to minimize the negative environmental impact of our operations.

Community

We want to make a positive contribution to the communities in which we operate by supporting chosen causes and initiatives that create a lasting difference, but always from a non-political and non-religious standpoint.

CODE OF ETHICS & ANTI-CORRUPTION

With our actions, we live these principles and build the reputation of a company that we can all be proud of. Our Code of Ethics and its supporting policies is an essential guide for us to ensure that we make the right decisions and take the right action, and that we apply the precautionary principle. The Ellos Group's Code of Ethics includes policies for Anti-bribery, Competition, Data Protection and Trade Sanctions to ensure compliance within the Group. During 2016, an internal Code of Conduct was rolled out in the organization, explaining how to act according to our Code of Ethics. The Code of Conduct was communicated to all employees, and all employees received a printed version of the Code of Conduct. The adherence to our Code of Conduct will be supported by a yearly online training for all employees. The Ellos Group works to counteract all forms of corruption and our Anti-bribery policy is the foundation for this work. The policy was discussed and approved by the Board in August 2015, and communicated to all employees in October 2015. All employees will have training on the policy yearly as part of the online training on the Code of Conduct. Also, a risk assessment has been conducted in all of the Ellos Group's operations, and specific training is given to the employees who are working in high-risk areas. We have identified a need to ensure that our suppliers abide by our policy on Anti-bribery, and will in 2017 update our Suppliers' Manual to include part of our Anti-bribery policy. Agreeing to, and signing, the Suppliers' Manual is compulsory for our suppliers. During 2016, there were no confirmed incidents of corruption within the Ellos Group.

EXTERNAL WHISTLEBLOWING SYSTEM

Our whistleblowing policy prescribes how to report concerns, and how reported concerns are addressed. In 2016, the Ellos Group introduced a whistleblowing reporting channel, which is provided by an external partner. The channel is a tool for our employees to report suspected or detected violations of the Code of Conduct or other corporate policies.

SUSTAINABILITY ISSUES IN OUR VALUE CHAIN

The industry in which we operate faces significant sustainability challenges. The textiles and apparel sector is a large user of natural resources, including water and fossil fuels. Other environmental topics in the fashion industry include heavy use of chemicals in the supply chain, and the industry's contribution to a "wear and tear" consumption pattern. Social issues are also significant, with complex supply chains and production in countries where there is a risk of poor working conditions and human rights adherence. As a responsible company in this sector, we seek to address these challenges by making better choices for the materials we use and by working closely with our suppliers to ensure fair working conditions and environmental management in our supply chain. We also strive for a timeless and high quality range, which our customers can keep using for a longer period of time and we encourage our customers to recycle their used clothes and textiles.

Design and purchasing

Our sustainability efforts begin at the drawing table, and in the process of design and purchasing we make several important decisions that affect the impact that our business has on economy, environmental and social issues. A key topic in this stage is materials. Our choice of using BCI cotton instead of conventionally grown cotton, for example, has an impact on the use of water and chemicals, as well as the social conditions in our supply chain. Supplier social and environmental assessments are also significant topics. Our choice of which suppliers that we entrust the production of our range to needs to be an informed decision, in which we require suppliers to adhere to our Code of Conduct.

Production

Production takes place outside of our direct control, at the production sites of our 283 suppliers. While not in our direct control, we recognize that our business can have a significant social and environmental impact in our suppliers' and sub-suppliers' operations. Fair working conditions, adherence to human rights and environmental issues such as the use of water and chemicals and effluents and waste, are important topics. Given the indirect control, the key topics for us are supplier social and environmental assessments. We strive to develop long-term relationships with our suppliers and work with them to ensure compliance with our social and environmental standards. Regular audits and corrective action plans are used to monitor and continually improve our social and environmental impact in production.

Transport

The transportation of our products, inbound from production to our central warehouse, and outbound to our customers, is carried out by transport companies. The key topics in this stage are energy and emissions, and we work with our transport providers to optimize the flow of goods and understanding how we can reduce the negative environmental impact of our transportation.

Operations

Our operations include our headquarters and logistics centre in Borås, and are under our direct control. Important topics in our operations are related to our responsibility as an employer, including occupational health and safety and diversity, and equal opportunity. The environmental impacts in our operations include energy, emissions and effluents and waste. Our interaction with customers, taking place at our operations, include the topic of physical customer mailing, which affects both the use of paper and the environmental impact of distribution.

Customers

Our customers also have a significant impact on sustainability in their care of our products, how long they keep them and whether they choose to recycle them after use. We do not have a direct impact on the behaviour of our customers, but we seek to influence them to a sustainable behaviour with, for example, clear instructions for how to care for the products best and by encouraging recycling, which we have identified as a significant topic.

TOPICS RELEVANT ACROSS THE ENTIRE VALUE CHAIN

Anti-corruption is a topic that we have identified as important, and this topic is not isolated in one of the value chain steps, but must be taken into account across all steps. In all interactions with suppliers, customers and other business partners, we must ensure that business is conducted in an ethical manner and that corruption is prevented.

Community engagement is also an important topic to us - we want to contribute positively to the communities in which we operate by supporting relevant causes and initiatives.

		OUR IMPACT				
		Direct		Indirect		
		Design & Purchasing	Production	Transport	Operations	Customers
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Mainly apparel and home interiors Own products 66% of sales 2016 External brands 34% of sales Approx. 9,000 own styles/year 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 283 suppliers Main sourcing markets 2016: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - China 48% - India 19% - Bangladesh 14% 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Inbound freight from suppliers: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Sea 91% - Road 7% - Air 2% Outbound freight to customers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Total permanent headcount: 618. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 580 in Borås, head office and logistics - 17 in Norway - 15 in Finland - 3 in Denmark 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1.6m active customers 5m customers shipments 2016: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Sweden 61% - Finland 19% - Norway 14% - Denmark 6%
		Anti-corruption				
		Community Engagement				
VALUE CHAIN ISSUES	Economic					
	Social	Supplier Social Assessment		Occupational Health & Safety		
				Diversity & Equal opportunity		
Environment		Material	Energy		Recycling	
		Supplier environmental assessment		Emissions		
				Effluents & Waste		
				Customer Mailing		

SUSTAINABLE MATERIALS

We want to offer our customers an attractive range of products, which have been designed and produced in a sustainable way. We can achieve this by making sustainable choices in design and purchasing, and by finding ways to increase the proportion of sustainable materials in our products.

Influence on stakeholder assessments and decisions

FOCUS ON MATERIAL TOPICS

In our sustainability strategy, and in this report, we focus on the topics that we have identified as material. The process of defining our material topics is described in more detail on pp 65-68 in this report. The potential topics were ranked in these two dimensions:

Influence on stakeholder assessments and decisions –

Expectations and concerns among key stakeholders. What do our stakeholders care about and what do they expect from us? According to our stakeholders, which topics are most important to the Ellos Group?

Significance of economic, environmental and social impacts –

The importance of the Ellos Group’s impact on economic, environmental and social topics. How does the Ellos Group’s operations affect sustainable development, and in which topics is our impact most significant?

Significance of economic, environmental and social impacts

REPORTING ON THE MATERIAL TOPICS - OUTLINE

In the following pages of this report, we will describe the Ellos Group's sustainability efforts in 2016, with our goals, actions and results achieved so far. The below table outlines the report sections and the material topics covered in each section.

Report section	Material Topics
Sustainability at Ellos Group	Anti-corruption
Sustainable materials	Materials
Supplier relations	Supplier social assessment Supplier environmental assessment
Environment	Reuse and Recycling Customer mailing Energy Emissions Effluents and Waste
Employees	Diversity and Equal opportunity Occupational Health & Safety
Community	Community Engagement

Our product range is a key focus area for our sustainability work – beginning with the design and purchasing decisions we make. Our design- and purchasing organization in Borås is constantly working to make good choices and to find new, more sustainable materials and production methods. About two-thirds of our range is our own brand styles, which gives us a good opportunity to influence the environmental impact of the goods at the design stage.

We set high standards for our products. In our product responsibility we assure that the products are safe, of good quality, do not contain dangerous chemicals and are produced with consideration for people, the environment and animal welfare. Our product policy defines materials that we exclude from all of our products, for example animal fur.

We have set up one main objective for sustainable materials. By 2020, 100% of the cotton in our own products should be sustainable cotton. We define sustainable cotton as organic cotton, recycled cotton or cotton from Better Cotton Initiative (BCI cotton). Cotton is, by a large margin, the most important fibre material in our textile range – some 78% of our own range product offering is cotton-based (2016). It is also a raw material with a high environmental impact, including water use, chemicals and working conditions in production.

In 2016, we took major steps towards 100% sustainable cotton. We moved from 10% sustainable cotton in 2015 to 46% sustainable cotton in 2016. The majority of the sustainable cotton is BCI cotton (read more about BCI on page 23). In specific product areas, such as baby clothing, 100% of our new cotton products sourced from the autumn-winter season 2016 were made from organic cotton.

Going forward, we will also seek to increase the proportion of other organic, recycled and innovative materials in all product areas.

	2014	2015	2016	Target 2020
Sustainable cotton, % of purchased cotton products*	2%	10%	46%	100%

* Estimate based on manual data analysis and excluding external brands. New systems to be implemented in 2017 will enable a better quality of tracking materials going forward.

SUSTAINABLE MATERIALS ACCORDING TO THE ELLOS GROUP

- **Organic fibres** – Certified by GOTS or OCS
- **Recycled fibres** – Focus on recycled cotton, polyester and polyamide certified by GRS and RCS
- **Eco-labeled products** - Svanen, Bra Miljöval or EU Ecolabel
- **BCI** – Cotton from Better Cotton Initiative
- **Lyocell** – a material with lower environmental impact than conventional materials, made through closed and controlled processes.
- **FSC-certified** - wood and fibers made from wood certified by Forest Stewardship Council.

© BCI

FUTURE FOCUS

- Participate actively with the BCI and Cotton Connect programmes to support the development of sustainable cotton production.
- Continue to build organizational capacity in sustainable material choices through training and developing design, purchasing and customer service functions.
- Develop a definition and plan for sustainable wood.
- Develop our range of external brands with a greater focus on sustainable products.
- Continue the process of mapping the chain of custody of our products further back in the supply chain.
- Increase use of recycled materials.

ELLOS
SUSTAINABLE
ASSORTMENT
**Conscious
Choice**

Looks good – makes a difference

Our Conscious Choice range is produced with respect for people and the environment. We use materials that are better choices for the environment – organic, recycled or innovative materials. Conscious Choice includes both basics and high fashion items – for everyday use and for special occasions.

JOTEX
SUCCESSFUL SHIFT TO
**Organic
Bedsheets**

During 2016, Jotex launched a new collection of bedding for children in 100% organic cotton, which replaced the present bedding offering for children. All products are GOTS certified organic cotton. Our customers have embraced the new bedding range for children, and we are very proud of it.

BETTER COTTON INITIATIVE AND COTTONCONNECT

The Ellos Group joined the Better Cotton Initiative in 2015. This Initiative exists to make global cotton production better for the people who produce it, better for the environment it grows in and better for the sector's future. Included in the training is, for example, how to manage safe harvesting, preventing child labour and how to create health and safety awareness at the farms. The BCI aims to transform cotton production worldwide by developing Better Cotton as a sustainable mainstream commodity.

CottonConnect was created in 2009 to deliver a market-driven approach to expanding economic opportunity, reducing poverty and protecting the environment. The organization works in India, Pakistan, China and Peru, impacting the lives of 700,000 farming families.

An example from the project with CottonConnect

The Ellos Group is supporting a BCI training program through CottonConnect - the BCI Implementing Partner, for farmers in Gujarat in India together with Gina Tricot. The program's duration is three years, from 2015 to 2018. Positive results began to show already in 2016.

One participant in the program is Shivrambhai Liladharbhai Pandya. Agriculture is his main source of income. He has been growing two main crops, groundnuts and cotton, but was not earning enough to provide a good life for his family. After joining the BCI Program with CottonConnect he learnt about good agricultural practices, like efficient water irrigation and better, reduced use of chemicals.

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After adopting the good agricultural practices that I learnt in the Cotton-Connect BCI training sessions I am expecting a hike in my income. I can already see some increase in my yield and I am hoping for some positive impact on my profit once harvesting and selling are over.

- Shivrambhai Liladharbhai Pandya

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Cotton is one of the **world's most important natural fibres**. It's used by nearly everyone on Earth every day, and supports 250 million people's livelihoods. It's a renewable natural resource, but only if we manage it responsibly.

Read more at
www.cottonconnect.org
www.bettercotton.org

ANIMAL WELFARE

Animal welfare is important to us. In our view, animals are, as sentient beings, entitled to be treated with respect. When our products are made of materials with animal origin, we require that the animals are treated well.

THE ELLOS GROUP:

- Does not sell products that contain real fur.
- Does not accept mulesing on merino sheep.
- Is restrictive in the usage of down and feathers and will only accept down and feathers as a by-product of meat. Live plucking is not accepted.
- Does not accept angora wool in any of our products.
- Will only accept leather as a by-product from meat.
- Only sells cosmetics that are not tested on animals.
- Does not sell products that contain materials derived from endangered species.

We are members of: Fur Free Alliance, Djurens rätt

CHEMICALS

We want to ensure that our products do not include any harmful, restricted or unnecessary chemicals. Our suppliers are required to follow strict regulations and tests are performed.

THE ELLOS GROUP:

- Does not sell products containing dangerous chemicals defined according to e.g. the regulations of the RoHS-directive and REACH regulation.
- Is restrictive in using:
 - PVC, antibacterial additives, biocides, flame retardants and phthalates in textile products, leather or shoes.
 - Moisture preventing products and moisture absorbers to avoid mould, for example Silica gel.
 - Perfluorinated compounds (PFC) as water resistance/repellent treatment. PFC was phased out in own textile products in 2015.

We are members of: Swerea – The Chemical Group

SUSTAINABLE PURCHASING PROCESS

In addition to sustainable design and material choices, our work processes also have other impacts on social and environmental sustainability in our value chain. With our move from mail order to an online business model, our product flow is more evenly distributed throughout the year, with less sharp peaks and improved planning possibilities, which makes it easier for our suppliers to plan for capacity and meet our orders within normal work hours. The online business model also implies a move away from the catalogue "in-stock guarantee", due to which we have historically had to use air freight to fill inventory shortages. As we removed the in-stock guarantee at the beginning of 2016, we have seen a reduction of emissions from air freight.

COLLABORATING WITH SFA

During 2016 we started collaborating with the Sustainable Fashion Academy (SFA). SFA works to equip apparel professionals with the knowledge and tools to build a sustainable future. The first step of the collaboration was a lecture and workshop with all designers and product managers in the Group. The next step is that 5 designers from Ellos will participate in the SFA online training program.

SUPPLIER RELATIONS

It is important to us and to our customers, employees and owners that our products are made with respect to the people who produce them as well as to the environment. We strive to ensure fair working conditions and adherence to human rights in our value chain and believe that a close dialogue and cooperation with our suppliers is necessary to achieve this. Regular audits and inspections are means to follow up on progress and identify if improvement is needed.

The Ellos Group's own brand products are manufactured by external suppliers, mainly in South East Asia. In 2016, we had 283 suppliers, of which 122 core suppliers (i.e. with sourcing volume above SEK 1 m), accounting for 86% of order value.

Our main sourcing markets are China, India and Bangladesh, with 48% of order value in 2016 sourced from China, 19% from India and 14% from Bangladesh. During 2016, the Ellos Group strategically moved production volumes from China to Bangladesh.

Supplier's Code of Conduct

- At the Ellos Group we think it is important to take responsibility for our actions and contribute to the development of a sustainable society. We want to ensure that the human rights of the people taking part in the production of our products are respected.
- Our Code of Conduct is based on the French standard ICS (Initiative Clause Social), which is equivalent to programs such as BSCI (Business Social Compliance Initiative), and follows international labour standards, such as International Labour Organization (ILO) conventions and declarations and the United Nations (UN) Guiding Principles on Business and Human Rights.
- The Code of Conduct covers important areas such as child labour, forced labour, discrimination, freedom of association, wages and working hours, health and safety in the workplace and environmental aspects.
- We require all suppliers to adhere to the Code of Conduct prior to starting any business relationship.
- The Code of Conduct applies to all suppliers and production units that are involved in the manufacture or supply of products to any of the companies included in the Ellos Group.
- The Code of Conduct sets forth the requirements that all suppliers must meet in order to do business with the Ellos Group. The suppliers are responsible for ensuring that these requirements are met at all factories involved in the manufacture of products for the Ellos Group.
- We also expect our suppliers to follow internationally accepted labour standards, including the ILO conventions, and to continually work on improving the working conditions for those involved in the production of our products.

SUPPLIER FOLLOW-UP PROCESS

We strive for all of our products to be manufactured in accordance with the Code of Conduct, under fair working conditions and with adherence to human rights. Our suppliers are required to adhere to our Supplier’s Code of Conduct. Prior to the first order, all suppliers should have a valid audit protocol.

In order to track progress, identify risks and improvement opportunities, and to support our manufacturers, we have a control and follow-up system in place with regular audits and inspections. Some of the audits are done by our main agent Kering Group Sourcing (KGS), and some through the independent audit institute Bureau Veritas. If improvement needs are identified in an audit, the supplier is required to introduce improvements that are outlined in a Corrective Action Plan. We seek to collaborate with our suppliers to ensure that they live up to our expectations.

Our main agent KGS carries out audits and inspections of the suppliers in their network, with a combination of their own inspections and semi-announced independent audits. All suppliers in the KGS network have been inspected and approved prior to inclusion on the list of suppliers. For external audits, Bureau Veritas is used by KGS.

Bureau Veritas utilizes protocols for on-site monitoring, which have been developed by KGS and the Ellos Group. The new audit protocol, implemented in 2015, includes 233 compliance questions, compared to 109 questions in the previous protocol. Inspections include confidential employee interviews, record testing, observations and management feedback. With a multipronged approach, auditors are able to consider various sources of information and utilize proven investigative techniques to corroborate evidence.

AUDITS AND INTERNAL ASSESSMENTS

The number of audits of our core suppliers has increased significantly over the past couple of years, nearly doubling from 44 in 2014 to 77 in 2015, and in 2016 the figure was 116. At the end of 2016, 95% of our core suppliers had been audited or inspected over 24 months, compared to 49% in 2015 and 33% in 2014.

During 2016, we changed our strategy for audits, from only focusing on core suppliers to including all suppliers. As the production of the Ellos Group's products is located in high-risk countries from a working condition perspective, there is a need of regular internal and third party inspections of all suppliers, independent of the sourcing volume the Ellos Group has at the supplier. In 2016, the Ellos Group reached 77% coverage of all suppliers with valid audits or inspections, up from 27% in 2015.

By 2020, our target is for 100% of our suppliers to have been audited, inspected or externally certified within 24 months. However, we expect to reach that target in 2017.

A cooperative approach for supply chain improvements

The conclusions of external audits are weighed together to a rating, reflecting the supplier's performance on sustainability with a rating from A to D.

For audits performed in 2014-2016, we saw an improvement in audit results, with 81% of factories audited in 2016 rated A, up from 75% in 2015. We strive to increase the proportion of A and B ratings and to work with suppliers with lower ratings to improve their rating.

15% of suppliers received a C or D rating with improvement needs. When improvement needs are identified, a Corrective Action Plan is issued, including a description of the non-compliance, recommended corrective action, a target date for when the corrective action is to be completed and a comment

AUDITS 2016 Supplier Audits	2014		2015		2016	
	#	%	#	%	#	%
Core Suppliers External audit or internal assessment <2 years	56	33	84	49	116	95
All Suppliers External audit or internal assessment <2 years	59	15	103	27	218	77

from the factory. Non-compliance identified in 2016 was mainly related to working hours and lack of documentation of wages and working hours. Depending on how serious the non-compliance is, another audit is scheduled to confirm progress within a set time frame. If issues are serious and not rectified, business will be terminated. In 2016, two of the Ellos Group's suppliers in the KGS network were terminated due to serious non-compliance, or failure to improve, translating into 0.7% of all suppliers.

Signing the accord for Bangladesh

In June 2016 the Ellos Group signed the Accord on Fire and Building Safety in Bangladesh, as Bangladesh is an increasingly important sourcing market for the Ellos Group. By signing the Accord, the Ellos Group commits that all of the factories producing garments for the Group are audited based on three different areas: fire safety, electricity and structural issues. The Group is also committed to drive remediation of Corrective Action Plans at the factories where the Ellos Group is Lead Brand. The role as Lead Brand makes us responsible for the improvement process towards the Accord, the factory and possibly other brands producing in the same factory.

More
Sustainable
Production

THROUGH COLLABORATION WITH STWI

The Ellos Group joined the Sweden Textile Water initiative, STWI, from its very beginning in 2010. The initiative was launched by major Swedish textile and leather brands and the Stockholm International Water Institute, and works with hundreds of textile factories in Bangladesh, China, Ethiopia, India and Turkey. The idea behind the initiative was to gain a better understanding of the water challenges faced by the industry and finding the right mechanisms to address them. STWI's aim is to generate economic, social and environmental savings from sustainable water use in textile and leather production.

Savings in 2016

In 2016, through direct engagement with the Ellos Group's suppliers in India and Bangladesh, STWI - saved more water than 7.25 million cubic meters which equals one day's need for more than 8.2 million human beings (based on the UN human rights to water minimum) - reduced electricity consumption by 464.3 MWh of electricity, which equals one day's electricity consumption for 92,800 rural households (based on World bank data on electricity consumption).

Read more at <http://stwi.se/>

TWO EXAMPLES FROM STWI'S INITIATIVES IN BANGLADESH WITH THE ELLOS GROUP

Saving 28 million litres of water annually

Shasha Denims Ltd. (SDL) is a denim fabric producer in Bangladesh and offers a full denim collection. The company produces its own denim fabrics and production capacity is around 19.7 million meters per year. In 2016, SDL reduced its water use to 78 litres per kg of denim produced from 110 litres per kilo. This gives annual savings of 28 million litres of water, as the weight of denim fabric produced amounts to around 875,000 kilos per year.

Source: SDL

Saving 50 tons of caustic soda per month

ACS Textiles Ltd. is a manufacturer and exporter of home textile products. The manufacturing process is vertically integrated with weaving, printing and dyeing. In 2016 the company achieved major environmental savings through a variety of measures. Some examples include automatic blow down controller for boilers, a reservoir of 15,000 litres for rainwater harvesting, reducing the use of underground water, solar panels, and a recovery plant for caustic soda, reusing 98% of caustic soda used, corresponding to 50 tons per month.

Source: ACS

In 2016, SDL reduced its water use from 110 litres per kilo of denim produced to 78 litres per kilo.

SUPPLIER RELATIONS IN QUALITY ASSURANCE AND ENVIRONMENT

In addition to the efforts we make to ensure fair working conditions in our supply chain, we work closely with our suppliers and make site visits and inspections to follow up on quality assurance and the environment management of our suppliers. Environment management is audited within the Bureau Veritas' audit protocol, as described on the previous pages.

The Ellos Group cooperates closely with suppliers in proactive quality assurance through laboratory testing and inspections, ensuring that the products delivered to the Ellos Group are already quality assured and that corrections or changes are made at the production site, before the products are shipped to the warehouse in Sweden.

Laboratory tests are carried out, mainly by Intertek's accredited laboratories, before production starts on all main orders. The tests are based on instructions in our product specifications, with tests including general testing, mechanic resilience, colour fastness, dimensional stability and chemical tests.

Inspections are conducted by third party agencies on all orders before shipping, to ensure that our quality requirements and kids safety demands are met, in order to approve consignment before shipment.

ENVIRONMENT

We strive to use natural resources efficiently and to minimise the negative environmental impact of our operations.

Our aim is to reduce both energy use and emissions relative to sales. Our largest impact in terms of emissions is caused by the transport of our products from our suppliers to our warehouse, and on to our customers. Another important cause of emissions has historically been the energy sources of electricity used at our head office and warehousing operations. By partly moving to renewable energy in 2015, and to 100% renewable energy in 2016, we have taken one important step in the right direction of reducing emissions from our operations. With transportation, we seek to minimize air freight and work more proactively with our transporters to reduce emissions. In connection with a major refurbishment of our head

office, we have implemented more energy-efficient solutions for lighting and heating.

Customer mailing is another area where we can reduce our environmental impact. From 2015 to 2016 we reduced our customer mailing by 49%. This means we are almost at the target level for 2020. The major reduction of paper comes from an improved tailoring of communication to our customers' needs, and a focus on communication in digital channels instead of through customer mailing.

		2016	2015	2014	Change 16 vs 15	Goal 2020
Energy Use (MWh)	Electricity	7,065	7,048	6,786	0%	12% decrease 2016-2020
	Heating	4,422	3,968	4,036	11%	
	Total	11,487	11,016	10,822	4%	
Share of renewable electricity		100%	71%	14%	29 ppts	100%
Greenhouse Gas emissions (CO2 tonnes)	Scope 2*	283	1,069	2,557	-74%	(See below)
	Scope 3**	5,906	7,167	6,613	-18%	
	Total Scope 2+3	6,189	8,236	9,171	-25%	
Greenhouse Gas emissions intensity: CO2 tonnes/SEK m sales		3,00	4,02	4,50	-25%	-20% vs 2015
Waste: % recycled waste in HQ and warehouse		88,6%	90,4%	89,5%	-1,8 ppts	95%
Customer mailing, tonnes		3,764	7,352	9,069	-49%	-50% vs 2015

* Scope 2: Indirect GHG emissions from consumption of purchased electricity, heat or steam.

** Scope 3: Other indirect emissions, such as, transport-related activities in vehicles not owned or controlled by the Ellos Group. Sources detailed in the following pages.

UNDERSTANDING AND ADDRESSING EMISSIONS

Inbound freight - the transport of products from our suppliers to the warehouse in Borås - is our largest source of greenhouse gas emissions, accounting for 63% of CO₂ emissions in 2016. Outbound freight to our customers accounts for 28% of emissions. In total, the transport of our products to reach our customers accounts for 91% of our CO₂ emissions.

Greenhouse Gas emission scopes as defined by GHG protocol, ghgprotocol.org

Scope 2:
Indirect GHG emissions from consumption of purchased electricity, heat or steam.

Scope 3:
Other indirect emissions, such as transport-related activities in vehicles not owned or controlled by the Ellos Group.

The table below outlines the changes in CO₂ emissions from 2015 to 2016. Total emissions in 2016 fell by 25% compared to 2015. This was partly driven by the move to renewable energy, which led to a 96% reduction in the emissions from electricity. In addition, emissions from inbound freight fell by 24% in 2016 due to lower volumes shipped.

Outbound freight emissions stayed at the same level. Fewer packages, but with a higher average weight, resulted in no change.

Business travel increased over the year, but the share of trips by train increased, leading to 6% lower emissions.

CO ₂ tonnes	2016	2015	2014	Change 16 vs 15	Comment
Heating	248	222	223	11%	Refurbishing of office buildings
Electricity	35	846	2,334	-96%	Change to 100% renewable energy
Subtotal Scope 2	203	1,069	2,557	-74%	
Inbound	3,906	5,143	4,328	-24%	Decreased inbound volumes shipped
Outbound	1,708	1,711	2,039	0%	
Business Travel	292	312	246	-6%	Larger share of trips to Stockholm by train, fewer long trips
Subtotal Scope 3	5,906	7,167	6,613	-18%	
Total	6,189	8,236	9,171	-25%	
CO ₂ g/SEK sales	3.00	4.02	4.50	-25%	

Sources: Electricity and heat: Borås Energi, Göteborgs Energi, Din El, Energimarknadsinstitutet
 Inbound freight: Transport suppliers
 Outbound freight: Postnord, DHL and the Ellos Group's estimates for returns.
 Travel: AKI travel, Resia

IDENTIFYING ENERGY SAVING OPPORTUNITIES

From 2010 to 2016, use of energy for electricity and heating at the Head Office and warehouse operations has fluctuated within a range of 10.2- 11.5 GWh. In 2016, energy use was 11.5 GWh, translating into a year-on-year increase of 4% compared to 2015. Energy use in relation to net sales was 5.58 MWh/MSEK, a 4% increase from 5.38 MWh/MSEK in 2015.

The increase in energy usage comes from heating. In 2016 we have been in the process of rebuilding our Head Office, and the building work is part of the explanation for the increase in energy use. In connection with the rebuilding, we have implemented some energy saving initiatives, which we expect to reduce our energy use from 2017.

During 2016 an energy audit (Energikartläggning) has been conducted, in accordance with the EU Energy Efficiency Directive. Based on the review, we have identified energy savings opportunities and set targets for reduced energy use for the coming years. The overall target is to reduce energy usage by 12% from 2016 to 2020.

Source: Borås Energi och Miljö

CHANGE TO RENEWABLE ENERGY

As of April 2015, the Ellos Group moved to 100% renewable energy, reducing the CO₂ emissions from electricity from 344 g/kWh in 2014 to an estimated 120 g/kWh 2015 and 5 g/kWh in 2016. Prior to the change of source, the Ellos Group's electricity sources corresponded to the Nordic markets' residual mix.

Sources: DinEl/ Göteborgs Energi, Borås Energi, Swedish Energy Markets Inspectorate. 2015 split estimated based on residual mix and monthly split 2014.

CHANGING MEANS FOR BUSINESS TRAVEL

Business travel by the Ellos Group increased slightly in 2016, from 2,101 one-way trips in 2015 to 2,112 in 2016, translating into emissions of 292 tonnes of CO₂ in 2016, mainly from air travel. The reduction in emissions, despite more trips, is driven by that more of the short trips to e.g. Stockholm, were made by train. In our travel policy we encourage our employees to travel by train for shorter distances.

	2016	2015	2014	Change 16 vs 15	Change 16 vs 14
Number of Trips	2,112	2,101	1,176	10	0%
- of which air	1,842	1,857	991	-16	-1%
- of which train	270	244	185	26	11%
-CO ₂ tonnes	292	312	246	-20	-6%

EMISSIONS FROM TRANSPORT

Inbound Freight

In 2016, the Ellos Group's total inbound shipments of products from our suppliers fell by 40% to 87 million tonkm. The main reason for the dramatic decline is a transition to leaner stock management, with reduced inventories in 2016. Total CO₂ emissions from inbound freight fell less than the tonkm, by 24% to 3,977 tonnes, translating into a 29% increase of emissions per tonkm compared to 2015, to 46 g. The main reason for the increase in emissions per tonkm is reduced efficiency in our sea freight. In 2017, we will work together with our freight partners to find solutions for how we can improve the emissions efficiency.

We seek to maximise the use of sea freight, which has significantly lower emission levels than air, at 20 g/tonkm versus 740 g/tonkm for air freight in 2016. Sea freight accounted for 91% of tonkm shipments in 2016, followed by trucks at 7%. Air freight accounted for only 2% of tonkm freight in 2016, and generated 32% of the Ellos Group's inbound freight emissions.

We are actively working to minimize our air freight. We pack our goods so that they take up as little space as possible during transport, and we strive to work more proactively with our carriers to improve transport efficiency and reduce emissions.

Outbound Freight

In 2016, we made 5 million shipments to our customers in the Nordic countries.

The average CO₂ emission per shipment was 0.16 kg. Emissions are higher in Finland compared to the other countries due to the longer distance from our warehouse. Between 2015 and 2016, the number of packages sent to customers fell by 1%, but with a 4% higher average weight due to changes in our product mix. This led to no change in CO₂ emissions compared to 2016.

We continually seek to optimize freight planning and filling rates in transport vehicles. Going forward, we will increasingly work proactively with freight providers, with environmental requirements as a part of the purchasing process.

	2016	2015	2014	Change 16 vs 15	Change 16 vs 15
Total number of Shipments	4,991,751	5,061,508	5,467,064	69,757	-1%
Average Shipment Weight, kg	2,09	2,01	1,85	0,08	4%
Total Shipped Weight, kg	10,427,000	10,153,600	10,130,509	273,400	3%
Total CO ₂ from outbound freight, kg	1,707,835	1,711,230	2,038,923	-3,395	0%

WASTE HANDLING

RECYCLING OF WASTE IN OUR OPERATIONS

Our waste mainly derives from the logistics operations, and 89% of the waste that we generate is sorted into fractions and recycled. We aim to further improve sorting into fractions and recycling, to recycle 95% of waste in 2020.

The total amount of waste in our Borås logistics operations and head office was 829 tonnes in 2016, a reduction of 10% on the previous year. Corrugated paper is by far the largest category at 69% of total waste volumes 2016. Office paper waste was reduced by 50% in 2016. Our employees are changing their behaviour, from printing papers to bringing their laptops to meetings instead.

A total of 94 tonnes, or 11% of the total waste volume, was not recycled in 2016. Most of this, 74 tonnes, was incinerated to generate district heating.

Partnering with the test bed project for textile recycling

Improving the degree of collection and recycling of used textile is an important step towards improving the environmental impact from the textile industry. At the Ellos Group, we want to contribute to the development of technology that would enable a high degree of recycling and high-value secondary products. During 2016 we became a partner to the Test Bed project for textile recycling, driven by Swerea IVF, The Swedish School of Textiles and a number of companies in the region. The Test Bed will be built around a number of pilot projects focusing on making use of waste textile material as a raw material in new processes for producing new materials and products in a number of application areas.

Yearly waste volumes, tonnes	2016	2015	2014	Change 16 vs 15
Corrugated paper	574	628	860	-9%
Wood	95	131	140	-27%
Metal	27	31	37	-11%
Office paper	15	30	34	-50%
Polyethene	24	11	25	118%
Other	0	0	17	0%
Subtotal recycled	735	831	1 112	-12%
Incinerable waste	74	69	111	8%
Unsorted waste	15	15	19	0%
Landfill	4	4	1	23%
Subtotal not recycled	94	88	130	7%
Total	829	918	1,243	-10%
Recycled, % of total waste	88.6	90.4	89.5	

ENVIRONMENT INITIATIVES IN OPERATIONS

Customer Mailings

- From 2013 to 2016, we reduced our paper mailing by almost 70%, or 8 500 tonnes, which corresponds to about 57,000 trees or a forest area of 54 football pitches annually. The reduction was made possible mainly by the transition to an online business model from the previous catalogue business of Ellos and Jotex, better tailoring of communication to our customers' needs, and a focus on communication in digital channels.
- By 2020, we are striving for 100% of paper mailing to be PEFC or FSC certified and for 100% of printing houses used to be certified by Nordic Ecolabel or similar. Today, our magalogues and lookbooks are printed on PEFC-certified paper, and 70% of our other mailings are printed in Nordic Ecolabel-certified printing houses.

New Packaging in Recycled Plastics

- Our deliveries to customers are made in a packaging made of plastic, which is efficient from a transportation space perspective if compared to e.g. paper cartons. On an annual basis, the Ellos Group uses 3.5 million packaging bags.
- In 2016, Ellos and Jotex introduced a new plastic packaging to customers. The bags are made of at least 80% PCR (postconsumer recycled) plastic, resulting in a reduction of our CO₂ emissions per bag by up to 60%.

Installing charging stations for electric/hybrid cars

The Ellos Group wants to participate in the transition to environmentally-friendly vehicles, and offer our employees charging stations for electric and hybrid cars at the workplace. During the autumn of 2016, ten charging stations for electric cars were installed at our office parking in Viared. The investment was partly financed by Klimatklivet.

Managing textile waste through collaborations

During 2016, the Ellos Group partnered with Emmaus Björkå by donating defective goods or textiles from our inventory that for various reasons are unsaleable. Through Emmaus Björkå the majority of the products are reused by selling the products in Emmaus Björkå's stores or as materials for job training. What can't be reused by Emmaus Björkå is sent to an external player for material recycling.

The Ellos Group also partnered with several other actors during the year to manage our textile waste. We started collaboration with Borås Idésömnad, a work integrating social enterprise in Borås, which sews sellable products from left-over textiles from our product development process. In addition, the Ellos Group collaborated with re:newcell in recycling non-sellable bed canopies to 100% new cotton fiber.

WORKING AT THE ELLOS GROUP

The Ellos Group aspires to be a modern and attractive workplace. In order to achieve this, we need to offer good working conditions, strong leadership, and a diverse workforce in terms of ethnic background, culture, gender and age. An inclusive corporate culture, in which we accept and leverage differences, is a prerequisite for an efficient, professional and profitable business, and an important component when we seek to recruit, develop and retain the right competence. At the Ellos Group, all employees shall have the same opportunities, rights and responsibilities, regardless of gender, gender identity or expression, sexual orientation, ethnic origin, religion, disability or age.

TOTAL
618
permanent
headcount

in December 2016. 580 of whom are based in the **Borås headquarters** and logistics operations. All of our employees, except in Denmark, are covered by collective bargaining agreements. We have 3 headcount based in Malmö, 17 headcount in Norway, 15 in Finland and 3 in Denmark.

92
Part time
headcount

526 of our permanent headcount (331 women and 195 men) are full-time headcount and 92 (83 women and 9 men) are part-time headcount. All employment data is retrieved from our personnel records.

STRIVING FOR Gender Equality AT ALL LEVELS

At Ellos Group we strive for even gender representation in the organization. This is important for us to in order to be an attractive employer, and to create the best working environment and a high performing team. Our target is to have an even gender representation in management, across departments and management levels by 2018.

Striving to reach our goal in 2018, we are working actively with identifying and supporting female employees with potential and ambition to be promoted as managers. We have also established a broad-based working group for equality and diversity, which works to ensure that the recruiting processes support our ambition.

	All Employees	Warehouse Employees	Office Employees
	67%	62%	70%
	33%	38%	30%
<30 years	7%	2%	9%
30-50 years	50%	48%	52%
>50 years	43%	50%	39%
	Managers	Senior Management Team	Board of Directors
	46%	38%	43%
	54%	62%	57%
<30 years	0%	0%	0%
30-50 years	68%	69%	57%
>50 years	32%	31%	43%

TARGETS FOR Equality & Diversity

- Even gender representation in management, across departments and management levels. Manager split 50/50 male/female by 2018.
- Increase the proportion of employees with foreign background (from 12,7% 2015), across departments and management levels, to better reflect society (Borås currently at 27%).

PROMOTING DIVERSITY AND INCLUSION

The Ellos Group’s operations are based on an open and inclusive attitude, where diversity and equality add value and where discrimination is not accepted. For us, diversity means a mixed group of employees with different gender, gender identity or expression, sexual orientation, ethnic origin, religion, disability and age. We are convinced that encouraging and leveraging differences will benefit our business, through a better understanding of our customers, more creativity and innovation, improved problem solving ability and a more interesting and dynamic workplace.

Besides gender equality, we are focusing on ethnic diversity as the first priority for our defined diversity targets. Our long-term target is for the ethnic diversity of our organization to reflect the society in which we operate.

Based on input from Statistiska Centralbyrån (SCB), we carried out a status analysis in December 2015 focusing on the ethnic diversity of our workforce in Sweden. The conclusion is that people with foreign background are currently under-represented, at 12.7% of the workforce, compared to the demographics in the society of Borås, at 27%. Our goal is to increase the proportion of employees with foreign backgrounds, across departments and management levels, to better reflect society. In 2017 we are planning to do a new analysis of the status of our workforce.

TRAINING MANAGERS IN DIVERSITY AND INCLUSION

In January 2016, the Group initiated collaboration with Mitt Liv, a social enterprise working for diversity and integration on the Swedish labour market. One part of the collaboration is a mentoring program, where employees from the Ellos Group volunteer as mentors for people with foreign origins for one year in the mentoring program Mitt Livs Chans. Read more about this mentoring program in “Community Engagement”.

In addition to the mentoring program, all managers at the Ellos Group had training in diversity and inclusion together with Mitt Liv during 2016. The training was the first in a training series, with the aim of creating awareness of recruiting managers and adopting a multi-level perspective on diversity in the organization.

Ellos Group	
Foreign background	Swedish background
13%	87%
Borås	
27%	73%

EMPLOYEE WELLNESS

At the Ellos Group, we continually strive to attract, develop and retain competent and motivated employees. A health-promoting way of working is therefore a priority for the Ellos Group. We work proactively to create a safe and healthy working environment and also to promote a healthy lifestyle among our employees.

Employee Survey

The Ellos Group's employees are a very important factor for our success. Therefore it is key for the Ellos Group to continually evaluate how we are doing as an employer, and how we can become even better. An employee survey helps us to create a platform for dialogue, transparency and openness, which are important parts of our corporate culture and core values. An employee survey is conducted on a bi-annual basis, and was carried out in 2015 with a response rate of 87%. 2015's results were as follows:

E-NPS

This measure tells us to what extent our employees would recommend the company as a place to work – attractive employer. Survey respondents are defined as ambassadors, passive or critics. The e-NPS is calculated as the percentage points of employees that are ambassadors minus the percentage points that are critics, and can range from -100 to +100. The Ellos Group was rated +15, compared to the external benchmark of +7. Our target is to reach +20 in the next employee survey that will be done in 2017.

Employee Satisfaction Index

This index includes questions about the following areas: respect, cooperation, impact, feedback, trust, information, holistic view, objectives, personal development, implementation and follow-up.

The Ellos Group's rating in 2015 was 82, which is a good rating, although there is still some room for improvement to the external benchmark at 86.

Proactive health promotion at Ellos Group

The Ellos Group has a long tradition of working strategically with employee health. Our vision is for all employees to feel better. Our proactive health improvement efforts include a health survey, which is carried out in all departments, with the aim to cover the entire Group within a two-year period. Based on the survey, a plan is developed for how to improve health in the department. Individuals that would benefit from a healthier lifestyle and motivation are offered personal health coaching. We have a Wellness Developer employed part-time who continually drives the health promotion work forward.

The Ellos Group offers its employees a wide range of activities to encourage a healthy lifestyle. Among other things we participate in an annual exercise challenge. There is a clear correlation between more exercise and less sick leave, which gives us a strong incentive to continue our work to motivate more employees to exercise regularly.

Continuous efforts to minimize sick leave and work related injuries

We continually follow up on the level of sick leave and aim to reduce sick leave with clear routines for following up and acting on reasons for absence.

We also track and follow up on all work-related injuries and incidents, seeking to minimize injuries by addressing risk areas.

The below table quantifies the number of work related injuries and reported incidents at the workplace, which did not lead to any personal injuries. We report and follow up incidents that could have led to injuries, to ensure that potential risks are addressed. The most common work-related injuries are related to back, neck and shoulder problems, where we seek to improve workplace ergonomics to mitigate the number of injuries.

Sick leave,% of ordinary work hours			
	2016	2015	2014
	5.41%	5.38%	4.78%
	Work related injuries	Reported incidents	
2016	32	32	
2015	22	34	
2014	30	41	

The Ellos Group has a robust system for occupational health and safety for our employees. Safety inspections are carried out on a regular basis in all buildings by the Group’s safety and health coordinator together with working environment representatives, and the maintenance manager. In conjunction to the inspection of the physical working environment, a review of the organizational and psychosocial work environment is carried out. Action plans are being made and followed-up on. 100% of the employees are covered by the occupational health and safety reviews.

TOP 100

Employer of the year

The Ellos Group **climbed to spot 88**, from last year's spot 102 in the student ranking performed by Universum of the most popular employers.

“That is a clear improvement, and particularly gratifying in view that we took a very big step closer to the top 50 positions already last year, as a so-called super-rocket.

- Johnny Eriksson,
HR Director at Ellos Group.

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2017-?

Employer branding company

The Ellos Group **is nominated** “Employer Branding Company of the Year 2017” by Universum.

COMMUNITY ENGAGEMENT

We want to make a positive contribution to the society in which we operate. We focus on supporting charitable causes and sponsorship programmes that are relevant to our employees, to our value chain and to our customers. In addition , we focus on initiatives where our employees can get involved and encourage our employees to get involved in our community initiatives. In 2016, 40 employees at Ellos Group contributed with their time and commitment to our community initiatives.

Examples of community engagement initiatives during 2016:

MENTORING IMMIGRANTS IN

Mitt Livs Chans

Today it takes on average **eight years** to get a first job when you come to Sweden from another country. That is something that the **Ellos Group would like to change.**

In January 2016, the Group initiated collaboration with Mitt Liv, a social enterprise working for diversity and integration on the Swedish labour market.

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Integration is one of today's major challenges. We want to do what we can to contribute to a greater diversity, both in society and in our company. The partner program with Mitt Liv is an excellent tool to better capitalize on the expertise that exists in our country in the form of newly arrived people.

*- Johnny Eriksson,
HR Director at Ellos Group.*

Through mentoring, training and expanded network of contacts, Mitt Liv wants to open doors for people of foreign origin. The Ellos Group's employees volunteer as mentors for one year in the mentoring program Mitt Livs Chans. The mentees are immigrants, who despite often extensive education have not managed to enter the Swedish labour market.

SPRÅKVÄNNER – SWEDISH SPEAKING TRAINING FOR IMMIGRANTS

Our local society currently has a major challenge in integrating immigrants, a challenge which is getting larger with the significant inflow of refugees. A key factor in getting established in society is to learn the language. Many immigrants lack connections to native Swedish speaking people to practice with and develop their speaking skills.

In cooperation with Borås Stad and Eurest, the Ellos Group is running a program, in which we invite a group of immigrants who study at SFI (Swedish For Immigrants) to regularly come to our office, have lunch, and practice their Swedish with “language friends” among the Ellos Group’s employees. During 2016, 30 of our employees have become language friends to 20 immigrants, in meetings that have proven an equally valuable experience for both parties.

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Our employees know that we make a contribution to society in an area where it is needed. It feels good to do something for other people and in addition you get to know colleagues from other departments. Everyone wins.

*- Annika Mårtensson,
Business Development
and Sustainability Director,
Ellos Group*

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THE ELLOS GROUP A DRIVING FORCE FOR DIGITAL COMPETENCE DEVELOPMENT IN BORÅS

During 2016, the Ellos Group has been an engaged partner to E-handelsstaden Borås in driving development of relevant education in the region. There is a lack of e-commerce trained personnel and the industry is growing by nearly 20% per year. In order to continue to ensure the availability of appropriate manpower we have together worked successfully for several new training options.

One of the main initiatives is our intensive collaboration with the University of Borås, which resulted in the start of the Master Program "Management of digital commerce" with start in the autumn of 2017.

Another focus has been continuous dialogues with the Swedish National Agency for Higher Vocational Education (YH), industry organizations, local politicians and the Västra Götaland competence platform. These dialogues paved the way for the 2-year polytechnic education "Digital Business Developer" which started in the autumn of 2016.

Read more at <http://ehandelsstaden.se/>

INTERNSHIPS FOR PERSONS IN BORÅS WHO ARE FAR FROM THE LABOUR MARKET

Through our involvement in the IF Elfsborg CSR initiative "We together" and the Borås City initiative "Jobb Borås" we regularly welcome several people who are far from the labour market for internships, which gives them valuable work experience.

*Wear it with a meaning
for women's equal rights.*

Ellos has taken an active standpoint for women's equal rights and against discrimination and violence against women, by being the first online company selling "One bracelet" supporting UN Women.

#strongbecause

During 2016, Ellos has also supported UN Women financially through the campaign #strongbecause, and with t-shirts for UN Women's participation at Almedalen.

GRI
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	102-2 Activities, brands, products, and services	The Ellos Group in brief, page 5-6 and corporate website http://www.ellogroup.com/	
	102-3 Location of headquarters	The Ellos Group in brief, page 5	
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	102-8 Information on employees and other workers	Employees – working at the Ellos Group, page 41-47	
	102-9 Supply chain	Sustainability issues in our value chain, page 12	
	102-10 Significant changes to the organization and its supply chain		Not Applicable –no significant changes took place in 2016.
	102-11 Precautionary Principle or approach	Sustainability at the Ellos Group, pages 9-14	
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GRI 102: General Disclosures 2016	102-15 Key impacts, risks, and opportunities	Interview with the President and CEO, page 3-4 Sustainability in our value chain, page 12 Focus on material topics, page 16	
	102-16 Values, principles, standards, and norms of behaviour	Sustainability at the Ellos Group, page 9-14	
	102-18 Governance structure	Ellos Group in brief, page 5	
	102-40 List of stakeholder groups	Stakeholder dialogue, page 62	
	102-41 Collective bargaining agreements	Employees – working at the Ellos Group, page 41-47	
	102-42 Identifying and selecting stakeholders	Stakeholder dialogue, page 62	
	102-43 Approach to stakeholder engagement	Stakeholder dialogue, page 62	
	102-44 Key topics and concerns raised	Stakeholder dialogue, page 62	
	102-45 Entities included in the consolidated financial statements	List of financial entities, page 69	
	102-46 Defining report content and topic Boundaries	Materiality process, page 66 Material issues and boundaries, page 67-68	
	102-47 List of material topics	Focus on material topics, page 16	
	102-48 Restatements of information		Not Applicable – no restatements have been made.
	102-49 Changes in reporting		Not Applicable –no significant reporting changes have been made.
102-50 Reporting period	About this report, page 70		

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	102-52 Reporting cycle	About this report, page 70	
	102-53 Contact point for questions regarding the report	About this report, page 70	
	102-54 Claims of reporting in accordance with the GRI Standards	About this report, page 70	
	102-55 GRI content index	GRI content index, page 70	
	102-56 External assurance	About this report, page 70	
Material Topics			
Anti-Corruption			
GRI 103: Management Approach 2016	103-1 Explanation of the material topic and its Boundaries	Material issues and boundaries, page 67-68 Sustainability issues in our value chain, page 12-13 Focus on material issues, page 67-68 Sustainability at the Ellos Group, page 9-14	
	103-2 The management approach and its components	Sustainability at the Ellos Group, page 9-14	
	103-3 Evaluation of the management approach	Sustainability at the Ellos Group, page 9-14	
	205-2 Communication and training about anti-corruption policies and procedures	Sustainability at the Ellos Group, Code of Ethics and Anti-Corruption, page 11	
	205-3 Confirmed incidents of corruption and actions taken	Group, Code of Ethics and Anti-Corruption, page 11	

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Materials			
GRI 103: Management Approach 2016	103-1 Explanation of the material topic and its Boundaries	Material issues and boundaries, page 67-68 Sustainability issues in our value chain, page 12-13 Focus on material issues, page 67-68 Sustainable Materials, page 15-24	
	103-2 The management approach and its components	Sustainable Materials, page 15-24	
	103-3 Evaluation of the management approach	Sustainable Materials, page 15-24	
	Additional Disclosure (not in GRI) Sustainable cotton, % of purchased cotton products	Sustainable Materials, page 15-24	
Energy			
GRI 103: Management Approach 2016	103-1 Explanation of the material topic and its Boundaries	Material issues and boundaries, page 67-68 Sustainability issues in our value chain, page 12-13 Focus on material issues, page 67-68 Environment, page 33-40	
	103-2 The management approach and its components	Environment, page 33-40	
	103-3 Evaluation of the management approach	Environment, page 33-40	
GRI 302: Energy 2016	302-1 Energy consumption within the organization	Environment, page 33-40 Identifying energy savings opportunities, page 36	
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Emissions			
GRI 103: Management Approach 2016	103-1 Explanation of the material topic and its Boundaries	Material issues and boundaries, page 67-68 Sustainability issues in our value chain, page 12-13 Focus on material issues, page 67-68 Environment, page 33-40	
	103-2 The management approach and its components	Environment, page 33-40	
	103-3 Evaluation of the management approach	Environment, page 33-40	
	305-2 Energy indirect (Scope 2) GHG emissions	Environment, page 33-40	
	305-3 Other indirect (Scope 3) GHG emissions	Environment, page 33-40	
	305-4 GHG emissions intensity	Environment, page 33-40	
Effluents and Waste			
GRI 103: Management Approach 2016	103-1 Explanation of the material topic and its Boundaries	Material issues and boundaries, page 67-68 Sustainability issues in our value chain, page 12-13 Focus on material issues, page 67-68 Environment, page 33-40	
	103-2 The management approach and its components	Environment, page 33-40	
	103-3 Evaluation of the management approach	Environment, page 33-40	
	306-2 Waste by type and disposal method	Environment, page 33-40	

GRI Standards	Disclosure	Page number(s) and/or URL(s)	Omission
Supplier Environmental Assessment			
GRI 103: Management Approach 2016	103-1 Explanation of the material topic and its Boundaries	Material issues and boundaries, page 67-68 Sustainability issues in our value chain, page 12-13 Focus on material issues, page 67-68 Supplier relations, page 25-32	
	103-2 The management approach and its components	Supplier relations, page 25-32	
	103-3 Evaluation of the management approach	Supplier relations, page 25-32	
GRI 308: Supplier Environmental Assessment 2016	308-1 New suppliers that were screened using environmental criteria	Supplier relations, page 25-32	
Occupational Health and Safety			
GRI 103: Management Approach 2016	103-1 Explanation of the material topic and its Boundaries	Material issues and boundaries, page 67-68 Sustainability issues in our value chain, page 12-13 Focus on material issues, page 67-68 Employees – working at the Ellos Group, page 41-47	
	103-2 The management approach and its components	Employees – working at the Ellos Group, page 41-47	
	103-3 Evaluation of the management approach	Employees – working at the Ellos Group, page 41-47	
GRI 403: Occupational Health and Safety 2016	403-1 Workers representation in formal joint management–worker health and safety committees	Employees – working at the Ellos Group, page 41-47	
Additional Disclosure (not in GRI)	Sick leave, % of ordinary work hours	Employees – working at the Ellos Group, page 41-47	
Additional Disclosure (not in GRI)	Number of work related injuries and reported incidents at the workplace	Employees – working at the Ellos Group, page 41-47	

GRI Standards	Disclosure	Page number(s) and/or URL(s)	Omission
Diversity & Equal Opportunity			
GRI 103: Management Approach 2016	103-1 Explanation of the material topic and its Boundaries	Page 67-68	
	103-2 The management approach and its components	Employees, page 43-44	
	103-3 Evaluation of the management approach	Employees, page 43-44	
GRI 405: Diversity and Equal Opportunity 2016	405-1 Diversity of governance bodies and employees	Employees, page 43-44	
Supplier social assessment			
GRI 103: Management Approach 2016	103-1 Explanation of the material topic and its Boundaries	Material issues and boundaries, page 67-68 Sustainability issues in our value chain, page 12-13 Focus on material issues, page 67-68 Supplier relations, page 25-32	
	103-2 The management approach and its components	Supplier relations, page 25-32	
	103-3 Evaluation of the management approach	Supplier relations, page 25-32	
	414-1 New suppliers that were screened using social criteria	Supplier relations, page 25-32	
	414-2 Negative social impacts in the supply chain and actions taken	Supplier relations, page 25-32	
Recycling (not covered by GRI standards)			
GRI 103: Management Approach 2016	103-1 Explanation of the material topic and its Boundaries	Material issues and boundaries, page 67-68 Sustainability issues in our value chain, page 12-13 Focus on material issues, page 67-68 Environment, page 33-40	
	103-2 The management approach and its components	Environment, page 33-40	
	103-3 Evaluation of the management approach	Environment, page 33-40	

GRI Standards	Disclosure	Page number(s) and/or URL(s)	Omission
Customer Mailings (not covered by GRI standards)			
GRI 103: Management Approach 2016 Additional Disclosure (not in GRI)	103-1 Explanation of the material topic and its Boundaries	Material issues and boundaries, page 67-68 Sustainability issues in our value chain, page 12-13 Focus on material issues, page 67-68 Environment, page 33-40	
	103-2 The management approach and its components	Environment, page 33-40	
	103-3 Evaluation of the management approach	Environment, page 33-40	
	Customer mailing, tonnes	Sustainable Materials, page 15-24	
Community Engagement (not covered by GRI standards)			
GRI 103: Management Approach 2016 Additional Disclosure (not in GRI)	103-1 Explanation of the material topic and its Boundaries	Material issues and boundaries, page 67-68 Sustainability issues in our value chain, page 12-13 Focus on material issues, page 67-68 Community engagement, page 48-52	
	103-2 The management approach and its components	Community engagement, page 48-52	
	103-3 Evaluation of the management approach	Community engagement, page 48-52	
	Number of employees engaged in community engagement projects	Community engagement, page 48-52	

STAKEHOLDER DIALOGUE

Our stakeholders are important sources of input and feedback to our materiality assessment process for the identification and prioritization of material topics that we focus on, both in action and in communication. We have identified, across our value chain, the people and the organizations with which we interact and for which our business has an important impact, and from these we have selected five main groups, based on relevance and interdependence: customers, employees, owners, suppliers and the local community. During 2014 and 2015, we engaged extensively with all of these groups, securing input from more than 900 people who have helped us understand which sustainability topics are important to them and why, what they expect from the Ellos Group in terms of sustainability performance and communication, and how we can seek to meet their expectations. The involvement of our stakeholders is a key part of our materiality analysis and has given us important insights for developing a sustainability strategy, as well as our sustainability reporting.

CUSTOMERS

Stakeholder Significance

Our customers are at the centre of everything we do and we strive to exceed their expectations.

Description of dialogue

We have ensured to seek input from customers across our four main markets – Sweden, Norway, Finland and Denmark – and from our three online stores – Ellos, Jotex and Stayhard. Our customers' views were collected through a survey conducted in November/December 2014, sent to 8,000 Ellos, Jotex and Stayhard customers in Sweden, Finland, Denmark and Norway, from which we received 600 responses. We also interviewed 60 current and potential customers in Gothenburg in December 2014 and held a customer web panel on the topic of sustainability, carried out by Scandinfo with 26 participants, in the autumn of 2015. We have an ongoing dialogue with our customers, mainly through customer service and social media interaction.

Highlighted sustainability topics

Customers find sustainability increasingly important and they try to make sustainable everyday choices. Topics that our customers find important to the Ellos Group include to ensure fair working conditions and human rights in the supply chain, through supplier social assessment, offering products made from sustainable materials and reducing the amount of paper in customer mailings.

EMPLOYEES

Stakeholder Significance

Our employees and their commitment are integral to our success and to our ability to define and reach our sustainability goals.

Description of dialogue

In November and December 2014, we carried out an employee survey, to which we received 212 responses. In addition, personal interviews were held with 38 employees from different parts of the organization. The dialogue with our employees is ongoing, through intranet feedback, information meetings, training and through the involvement of our employees in our day-to-day sustainability work.

Highlighted sustainability topics

The Ellos Group's employees show a very high level of interest in, and commitment to, sustainability and believe that it is business critical. The topics that our employees see as key priorities include ensuring supplier social assessment, increasing the proportion of sustainable material in our customer offering, anti-corruption and minimizing the negative environmental impact of our operations, including energy use and carbon emissions.

SUPPLIERS

Stakeholder Significance

We need to work closely with our suppliers to jointly manage the sustainability impacts of our supply chain.

Description of dialogue

We interviewed both our own brand suppliers and one brand supplier, in December 2014 and November 2015. We have regular interaction with our suppliers, through the purchasing process, as well as through the regular follow-up of our code of conduct by audits and corrective action plans.

Highlighted sustainability topics

Our suppliers express a high focus on sustainability, both from the Ellos Group and other customers. In their view, the Ellos Group should focus on value chain topics, including supplier social assessments, sustainable materials, sustainable purchasing processes and chain of custody of materials.

OWNERS

Stakeholder Significance

Setting the tone from the top is necessary to truly integrate sustainability into our business model.

Description of dialogue

We interviewed Anders Halvarsson, Livehill, and David Samuelson, Nordic Capital, in December 2014 and Emma Englén, Nordic Capital, in November 2015. Our owners stay close to our sustainability work and require regular reporting on our progress. They also make sure that sustainability topics are regularly reviewed by the Board of Directors.

Highlighted sustainability topics

The owners expect the Group to deliver increased shareholder value. They take a long-term view on sustainability and actively support the Group in sustainability matters, with a focus on governance, managing risks and finding opportunities in the value chain. Highlighted sustainability topics include anti-corruption and business ethics, sustainable materials and supplier social assessment.

SOCIETY

Stakeholder Significance

A good relationship with our local society in Borås is important to the Ellos Group, especially as it affects our ability to recruit and retain highly skilled employees. The Ellos Group is also an important contributor to society in Borås, as the city's second largest private employer and a supporter of several local community initiatives.

Description of dialogue

We interviewed Anders Glemfelt, Enterprise relations manager, Borås Stad, in November 2015.

Highlighted sustainability topics

Important topics for our local community are community engagement, employment, occupational health and safety and indirect economic impact.

Interviews: Bril Lacno, KGS, Henrik Wahlgren, Brink Textiles, and Tina Foghammar, Twist & Tango, Dec 2014, and Anders Rosén, C Jahn AB, Nov 2015

MATERIALITY PROCESS

The materiality process is an integral part of our sustainability strategy development, through which we assess our current status, set priorities, define goals and develop strategies. It is also the basis on which we have defined the content of our sustainability reporting.

1. Identify

We started our materiality process in 2014 by identifying a large number of potential sustainability topics, based on an analysis of our value chain and a broad-based review of input, including the UN Global Compact principles, GRI aspects, ILO labour standards, sustainability reports from other companies in our industry and industry risk assessments such as those included in the CDC Toolkit on ESG for Fund Managers (2010).

2. Prioritize

In dialogue with our key stakeholders, as described above, we assessed the importance of topics from their perspective by asking them to prioritize which topics were most important to the Ellos Group. In parallel, we analysed our value chain and held workshops with management to align on which topics were to be prioritized from a strategic point of view, and in which economic, environmental and social topics that the Ellos Group's impact is most significant.

3. Validate

The prioritized topics, as well as our sustainability principles, were discussed and aligned in two management team workshops and one workshop with two of the Board of Directors. At this point we also conducted some additional interviews with stakeholders (suppliers, owners and society) and held a customer focus group on the subject of sustainability to validate our priorities. A sustainability plan, outlining prioritized topics and short and long-term goals and strategies, was finally presented to and approved by the Board of Directors in December 2015.

4. Review

The sustainability plan is regularly reviewed by the management team and at least annually by the Board of Directors. We find the original analysis to remain valid and have decided to continue with the same focus topics, as reflected in the choice of topics in this report, as well as our 2017 targets and plans.

MATERIAL TOPICS & BOUNDARIES

The table below outlines our material sustainability topics and their boundaries – detailing where in our value chain each impact occurs.

Priority	Topic	Intent	Boundaries – where the impact occurs	Report section
Focus	Materials	We will increase the proportion of sustainable materials in our products, thereby offering our customers a better choice and reducing our negative environmental impact.	In our organization, mainly the design and purchasing functions	Sustainable materials
	Supplier social assessment	By working closer with our suppliers, we strive to ensure fair working conditions and adherence to human rights in our supply chain.	At our suppliers and sub-suppliers, mainly in the Far East (China, India and Bangladesh).	Supplier relations
	Anti-corruption	We will ensure that policies and principles are communicated to and understood by all employees and business partners.	In our organization and the organizations of our business partners.	Sustainability at the Ellos Group
Meet expectations	Recycling	We will encourage our customers to recycle used clothes and textiles.	Among our customers	Environment
	Customer mailing	We will tailor our customer mailing to meet customer needs while reducing the amount of mailing.	In our organization, mainly the marketing function	Environment
	Supplier environmental assessment	We strive to work closely with our suppliers to reduce the negative environmental impact of their operation, e.g. reducing the use of water and chemicals.	At our suppliers and sub-suppliers, mainly in the Far East.	Supplier relations

Priority	Topic	Intent	Boundaries – where the impact occurs	Report section
Develop	Energy	We seek to minimize the use of energy in our operations.	In our organization, mainly our headquarters (Energy use by our suppliers covered in supplier environmental assessment)	Environment
	Emissions	We seek to minimize the greenhouse gas emissions in our value chain, mainly by focusing on inbound and outbound transports.	Mainly during transport, managed by external transport companies.	Environment
	Diversity and Equal opportunity	Diversity and inclusion makes our organization stronger.	In our organization.	Employees
Maintain	Community engagement	We support chosen causes and initiatives that create a lasting difference.	In the communities where we, or our suppliers, operate.	Community
	Effluents and Waste	We seek to minimize the amount of unrecycled waste from our operations.	In our organization. (Effluent and waste at our suppliers covered in supplier environmental assessment)	Environment
	Occupational Health and Safety	We have a strong commitment to employee health and safety.	In our organization	Employees

LIST OF EXTERNAL INITIATIVES

The Ellos Group is involved in or endorses the following externally-developed economic, environmental and social charters, principles or initiatives:

Charter/ principle/ Initiative	Description of the Ellos Group's involvement
ILO conventions	We expect all our suppliers to follow the ILO conventions. Our Code of Conduct follows the ILO conventions.
UN Guiding principles on Business and Human Rights	We expect all our suppliers to follow internationally accepted labour standards. Our Code of Conduct follows the UN guiding principles on Business and Human Rights.
Initiative Clause Social (ICS)	Our Code of Conduct is based on the French standard ICS (Initiative Clause Social)
The Accord on Fire and Building Safety in Bangladesh	The Ellos Group signed the Accord on June 30th 2016

LIST OF MEMBERSHIP OF ASSOCIATIONS

The Ellos Group is a member of the below listed associations:

Association	The Ellos Group's role
Better Cotton Initiative	Active member.
CottonConnect	Partner to CottonConnect, running a project in India together with Gina Tricot
Kemikaliegruppen	Active member
Fur free alliance	Active member
Swedish Shoe Environmental Initiative (SSEI)	Active member
CSR Västsverige	Active member
Djurens rätt	Active member
EL-Kretsen	Active member
STWI	Active member, working with five of the Ellos Group's factories in India and Bangladesh
Swedish Standards Institute (SIS)	Active member
TMR	Active member
Svensk Handel	Active member in several interest groups, e.g. Product Safety, Animal Welfare and T4RI

LIST OF FINANCIAL ENTITIES

The below list includes all financial entities in the Ellos Group. The operations of all entities in the group are covered by this report.

Financial Entity	Organization Number	Country
Ellos Group Holding AB	556857-8511	Sweden
Ellos Holding AB	556831-9114	Sweden
Ellos Group AB	556217-1925	Sweden
Ellos AB	556044-0264	Sweden
Jotex Sweden AB	556249-7106	Sweden
Ellos Finans AB	556311-5301	Sweden
Ellos Tili OY	1442185-0	Finland
Ellos Finland OY	1442131-6	Finland
Ellos Norway Holding AS	879478642	Norway
Ellos Norway AS	832005622	Norway
Ellos Denmark A/S	24927814	Denmark
Stayhard Holding AB	556783-8858	Sweden
Stayhard AB	556713-8077	Sweden
Stayhard AS	990698481	Norway
FAAD AB	559027-6407	Sweden

ABOUT THIS REPORT

This is the second sustainability report from Ellos Group, with full legal entity name Ellos Group Holding AB (publ) and organization number 556857-8511. Our sustainability reporting cycle is annual and follows the calendar year. This sustainability report covers our sustainability performance for the financial and calendar year 2016. The most recent previous report, covering 2015, was published on March 29, 2016. This report has been prepared in accordance with the GRI Standards: Core option. The content of this report is based on our materiality analysis, which includes a stakeholder dialogue and a value chain assessment. This report covers the activities of the Ellos Group, including its wholly-owned subsidiaries, sales offices in Norway, Finland and Denmark and our headquarters and wholesale operations in Borås, Sweden. No significant changes have occurred during the reporting period of this report.

This report has not been externally audited.

The Ellos Group's sustainability report is available at the Group's website: ellosgroup.com.

*For questions about this report,
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